

Microdetermination of Metals in Organometallic Compounds by the Oxine Method, Closed Flask or Open Tube Decomposition*

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Drops of nitric-perchloric acid and hydrogen peroxide digestion mixture, placed in a test tube, have utilized for decomposition of organometallic compounds containing Al, Fe, Cu, U, Co, Ti, Ni, La, Th or Mo. The open tube method, besides being efficient, is convenient and rapid, decomposition occurs within 5-10 minutes. The metal content is estimated using 8-hydroxyquinoline followed by a gravimetric or a titrimetric determination. For every sample weight three results are obtained using three different methods, the average per cent error for the determination is ± 0.15 , ± 0.11 and ± 0.14 , respectively. The oxygen flask combustion procedure was extended to Mo, La and Th and the average per cent error for the determination is ± 0.23 , ± 0.14 and ± 0.18 , respectively.

In the analysis of organometallic compounds, the method of decomposition together with the method of estimation of the metal content are the two problems involved. The mutual relationship which exists between the method of decomposition and the method of determination to follow is to be taken into consideration.

Decomposition by incineration to sulphate, oxide or the metal itself is not always so reliable¹, after decomposition, gravimetric estimation of the metal content has to go through the problem of selecting the suitable weighing form. Besides the probable danger of loss of substance by sublimation, also few number of metals yield forms stable enough to be recommended for a gravimetric finish. Wet decomposition in sealed tube, using different digestion mixture, has been widely applied some years ago. However, the Carius decomposition, being a time consuming-task, lost much of its popularity. Kjeldahl digestion resembles the Carius decomposition in that both are efficient for mineralising metals from their difficultly decomposable compounds. The relatively high concentration of sulphuric acid restricts, to some extent, the applicability of the technique, neutralization of the acid may cause co-precipitation as a result of the high salt concentration produced. Fusion in the nickel bomb is a rapid means for decomposition, but suffers from the danger of co-precipitation due to the same above reason.

The closed-flask method of combustion² has been applied for the analysis of organometallic compounds. The microdetermination of Cd, Mg, U, Zn, Co, Mn, Ti, Cu, Pb, Al, Fe, Ni, Ca and Bi in organometallic compounds using 8-hydroxyquinoline (Oxine) following combustion by the

O-Filled Flask method have been described³⁻⁵; gravimetric and titrimetric procedures were used for the estimation of the metal content. To ensure quantitative combustion, mixing the sample with a Flux sometimes proved a necessity^{4,5}. The use of fairly concentrated (1:1) acid as absorbent, followed by boiling of the absorption solution was found necessary for combustion of compounds containing iron, aluminium, nickel or bismuth⁵. Moreover, a platinum gauze sample holder is usually satisfactory but a Pyrex glass or silica spiral is used with organobismuth⁵ compounds to avoid alloy formation with the platinum holder. This diversity together with the drastic conditions of absorption solution inhabit the merit of the O-filled flask method as a simple and general tool for decomposition of organometallic compounds.

Tauchitani, Tomita and Ueno⁶ reported a rapid, convenient and efficient method for decomposing a wide variety of metal chelates; the sample being placed in an open tube charged with a digestion solution of concentrated nitric acid alone or mixed with sulphuric or perchloric acid. Although the method seems promising, a further attempts have been reported to test the capability of the technique for mineralising metals from their organometallic compounds.

In the present work, the open tube method proved satisfactory for decomposition of Al-, Co-, Ti-, U-, Cu-, Fe-, Ni-, La-, Th- or Mo-containing organic compounds. A procedure for combustion of organic compounds containing La, Mo and Th using the closed-flask method is also described. It seems that there is no other method for the determination of any of the three metals in organic

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Fig. 2. Titration of H_3PO_3 ($0.4NH_4SO_4$) or NaH_2PO_3 ($8.0NH_4SO_4$) with $KMnO_4$ in presence of 1% NaF .

	Total volume
(A) 2.5 ml $0.0250M H_3PO_3$, $0.0397N KMnO_4$	25
(B) 2.5 ml $5.18 \times 10^{-4}M H_3PO_3$, $7.95 \times 10^{-4}N KMnO_4$	25
(C) 2.5 ml $5.18 \times 10^{-4}M H_3PO_3$, $7.95 \times 10^{-4}N KMnO_4$	10
(D) 5 ml $5 \times 18 \times 10^{-5}M H_3PO_3$, $7.95 \times 10^{-5}N KMnO_4$	10
(E) 1.5 ml $5.18 \times 10^{-5}M H_3PO_3$, $7.95 \times 10^{-5}N KMnO_4$	10
(F) 4 ml $0.058M NaH_2PO_3$, $0.0793N KMnO_4$	25
(G) 2.5 ml $5.85 \times 10^{-4}M NaH_2PO_3$, $7.63 \times 10^{-4}N KMnO_4$	25
(H) 2.5 ml $5.85 \times 10^{-4}M NaH_2PO_3$, $7.63 \times 10^{-4}N KMnO_4$	10
(I) 3 ml $1.17 \times 10^{-4}M NaH_2PO_3$, $1.59 \times 10^{-4}N KMnO_4$	10
(J) 3 ml $5.85 \times 10^{-5}M NaH_2PO_3$, $7.93 \times 10^{-5}N KMnO_4$	10

Discussion

Hypophosphorous acid and hypophosphite are known to be oxidised quantitatively with $KMnO_4$ in acid solutions containing fluoride ions in presence of Cu^{+2} ions as catalyst and can be titrated either visually or potentiometrically to yield phosphorous acid and phosphite respectively as follows :

The practical importance of the amperometric titrations is due to their simplicity and rapidity. The equivalence point can be determined from few

readings on each side of the end point whereas in the potentiometric titration, the equilibrium becomes sluggish as the concentration of the reactants decreases. In amperometric titration, it is not necessary to apply an external e.m.f. since $KMnO_4$ is reduced at almost zero applied e.m.f. as long as the solution contains reducible substances. Also, it is not necessary to deaerate the solutions before carrying out the titration because oxygen is not reduced under these conditions contrary to the case when titrations are carried out at more negative potentials. The titration curves are nearly reversed L-shaped curves and the intersection of the two branches of the curve gives the equivalence point which is reproducible. For quantitative determination, 10 samples between $5 \times 10^{-2}M$ and $5 \times 10^{-5}M$ concentrations of each reductant were selected and for every sample the titration was repeated ten times. The average error in the determination was well below $\pm 1\%$. The amperometric method can be considered as a good analytical tool for microdetermination of P(I) and concentrations of hypophosphorous acid and hypophosphite corresponding to amounts of phosphorus ranging from $2.4 \mu g$ to $2.01 mg$ and from $5.4 \mu g$ to $3.62 mg$ respectively can be determined accurately.

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